

From carbon to climate action: harnessing basalt for geological carbon dioxide (CO₂) storage onshore and offshore

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Abstract: Abating emissions and reducing atmospheric concentrations of carbon dioxide (CO₂) are crucial in avoiding catastrophic climate change. Basalt reservoirs offer suitable CO₂ storage sites and are present onshore and offshore. This study compares the geological, economic and social aspects of CO₂ storage in both domains using two basalt formations from the Republic of Ireland: the Limerick Igneous Suite and the Druid Formation. Offshore reservoirs offer larger storage resources but are more expensive to develop. Nevertheless, both offer gigatonne-scale theoretical CO₂ storage. Reviewing public perception studies on wind energy demonstrates that the commonly held belief that offshore projects face less opposition owing to their distance from communities has been dispelled, while similar studies on carbon capture and removal show no preference for onshore or offshore development. Instead, a general scepticism towards carbon removal is observed, with concerns that it hinders broader decarbonization efforts. The desire of all stakeholders to be involved throughout project development is consistently observed. Lessons from offshore natural gas projects highlight the consequences of failing to engage with local communities. The Republic of Ireland has significant potential to deploy geological CO₂ storage in basalt reservoirs, but policy hurdles such as legal limits on storage volumes must be overcome to reconcile climate ambition and legislative capacity.

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Human-induced climate change is a major societal challenge of this century (Metz *et al.* 2007), driven by anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Among these emissions, carbon dioxide (CO₂) has the largest impact owing to its high atmospheric concentration and long residence time (Metz *et al.* 2005, 2007). Therefore, rapid societal decarbonization coupled with reducing atmospheric concentrations of CO₂ are key to addressing this challenge. This includes capturing CO₂ emissions from point-sources like power stations using carbon capture and storage (CCS) and removing existing CO₂ from the atmosphere using carbon dioxide removal (CDR) techniques (Metz *et al.* 2005; Bui *et al.* 2018; IPCC 2022). Both CCS and CDR utilize geological reservoirs to provide durable storage for CO₂, either as a fluid in the pore spaces of the reservoir rock or through chemical reactions with the reservoir rock to form stable solid minerals (Seifritz 1990; Lackner 2003).

Basalt reservoirs offer significant potential for CO₂ storage, particularly through *in situ* mineralization, and are widely distributed globally, both onshore and offshore (Pilorgé *et al.* 2021). Existing CO₂ mineralization projects have focused on onshore basalt layers (e.g. McGrail *et al.* 2011; Clark *et al.* 2020; Fedorik *et al.* 2023; Seyyedi and Consoli 2024) while certain offshore sites have been proposed for their geological storage potential (e.g. Snæbjörnsdóttir and Gislason 2016; Pereira and Gamboa 2023). However, with a large volume of mapped basaltic rock mass found offshore (Pilorgé *et al.* 2021; Millet *et al.* 2024), further work is needed to compare the benefits and challenges of developing CO₂ removal and storage projects onshore or offshore.

Using legacy geological and geophysical data from hydrocarbon and mineral exploration, this study explores the geological and economic potential of using two basalt layers, one onshore and one offshore, for CO₂ storage in the Republic of Ireland. Furthermore, a review of the public perception regarding onshore and offshore project development, including CCS and wind energy projects, provides insight into stakeholder concerns and lessons from past failures in other offshore industries. The results have significance for the Republic of Ireland's approach to achieving its climate goals through emission reduction and offsets using CCS and CDR, with broader implications for global CCS and CDR projects aiming to durably store CO₂ in geological reservoirs.

Greenhouse gas emissions, policy and outlook in Ireland

In 2021 the government of Ireland announced plans to reduce GHG emissions by at least 50% from the 2018 baseline (c. 62 million tonnes of CO₂ equivalent, or MtCO₂eq) by 2030 (Fig. 1) and achieve net zero GHG emissions by 2050, following a legally binding amendment to the Climate Action and Low Carbon Development Act. Ireland's GHG emissions have dropped from approximately 69 MtCO₂eq in 2005 to approximately 55 MtCO₂eq in 2023 (Fig. 1; Environmental Protection Agency 2024). However, current projections indicate that Ireland is not on track to meet its 2030 target with estimated reductions falling significantly short of the 50% goal (Environmental Protection Agency 2025).

Fig. 1. Ireland's greenhouse gas emissions (in MtCO₂eq) from 2005–23 and future total emissions target according to Climate Action and Low Carbon Development (Amendment) Act (2021). ETS, Emission Trading Scheme. Source: Data from Environmental Protection Agency (2024) and European Commission (2024).

The European Union has demonstrated a strong commitment to achieving carbon neutrality by 2050 and has implemented a variety of policies to support this, including the European Green Deal and the subsequent European Climate Law. The EU's Emission Trading Scheme (EU ETS) supports these ambitious climate goals. First introduced in 2005, the scheme operates as a carbon trading system using a 'cap-and-trade' principle and sets maximum carbon emission allowances for various industries, within which companies can buy or sell their emission allowances. The EU ETS was revised in 2009 to support the geological storage of CO₂ (i.e. CCS) and considers these captured emissions as 'not emitted' provided they comply with the EU CCS Directive. This provides a financial incentive for the development of CCS within the EU as emitters can avoid surrendering their allowances for the captured CO₂. Policymakers are exploring the integration of CDR into the EU ETS, but this has not yet been fully implemented as of June 2025.

Conversely, legislative support for the geological storage of CO₂ from CSS or CDR has lagged in Ireland. While the Climate Action Plan 2025 does mention CCS as a necessary technology, it lacks a clear roadmap or enabling legislation to support deployment (Government of Ireland 2025). Similarly, while Article 4 of the European Communities (Geological Storage of Carbon Dioxide) Regulations (European Communities 2011) allows up to 100 kt of CO₂ to be stored in geological reservoirs for research purposes, larger scale industrial geological carbon storage (in either the mega- or gigatonne range) remains illegal in the Republic of Ireland (Fig. 2). There is also no legislation at present for national CO₂ transport within Ireland, and the country has not signed the 2009 amendment to the London Protocol, which would permit international transport of CO₂. When mapped onto both the

typical development steps of a CO₂ storage project and the techno-economic resource pyramid (Bradshaw *et al.* 2007), the impact of these policies becomes apparent. These legislative roadblocks look increasingly incongruent given the clear synergies between current European and Irish goals and the significant economic and societal benefits for Ireland in meeting EU-mandated emissions targets (Fig. 2).

Carbon capture and geological storage techniques

Techniques used to capture CO₂ are typically subdivided into nature- and technology-based methods. Nature-based methods rely on enhancing natural processes which remove CO₂ from the atmosphere, including photosynthesis, the weathering of silicate rocks and the uptake of CO₂ in the Earth's oceans (e.g. Bach *et al.* 2019; Bullock *et al.* 2021). Conversely, technology-based methods use chemical reactions to capture CO₂ and store it in a stable form, often in geological reservoirs (Gough and Upham 2011; Ringrose 2020; McQueen *et al.* 2021) (Fig. 3).

Geological storage is achieved by either injecting CO₂ as pure fluid or dissolving it in water to form an aqueous mixture for injection (Dipple *et al.* 2021). Pure CO₂ is typically stored at depths greater than 800 m, where the ambient temperature and pressure exceed the critical point of CO₂ (31°C and 7.3–7.4 MPa), making it a supercritical fluid. Supercritical CO₂ has the density of a liquid but the viscosity of a gas (Bui *et al.* 2018; Ringrose 2020). This allows more CO₂ to be stored per unit volume in the subsurface compared with surface conditions, while also enabling it to flow more readily through a porous geological reservoir. Once injected for storage, the CO₂ will largely remain as a free-phase plume within reservoirs of

Fig. 2. Storage project development stages and legislative roadblocks currently prohibiting industrial geological storage of CO₂ matched to the four levels of the techno-economic resource pyramid of Bradshaw *et al.* (2007).

Fig. 3. (a) Schematic overview of CO₂ capture from both point-source emitters and from the atmosphere and storage in igneous reservoirs through *in-situ* mineralization. (b) Graph illustrating the various trapping mechanisms active in sedimentary reservoirs. (c) Graph illustrating the various trapping mechanisms active in igneous reservoirs. Note the greater degree of mineral trapping through mineralization in igneous reservoirs owing to greater availability of reactive cations. Source: Adapted from Kim *et al.* (2023) and references therein.

sedimentary rocks and thus may be vulnerable to leakage caused by post-injection tectonic activity or poorly sealed boreholes (Fig. 3). Over time, some of the CO₂ will react with the reservoir rock to form carbonate minerals, providing a more stable, solid form of storage through *in situ* mineralization. The extent of mineralization depends on the type of reservoir rock used (Fig. 3). This study will focus on CO₂ storage through *in situ* mineralization.

CO₂ mineralization involves the reaction of CO₂ with metals to form carbonate minerals. Divalent cations (positively charged ions capable of forming two covalent bonds) such as Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺ and Fe²⁺ react with CO₂ to form carbonate minerals such as calcite (CaCO₃), magnesite (MgCO₃), dolomite (CaMg(CO₃)₂) and siderite (FeCO₃) for stable long-term storage (Metz *et al.* 2005; Fig. 3). Mafic and ultramafic rocks are, by definition, abundant in minerals containing these cations such as plagioclase (CaAl₂Si₂O₈), olivine ((Mg, Fe)₂SiO₄), pyroxene ((Ca, Mg, Fe)₂Si₂O₆), amphibole ((Ca, Mg, Fe)₇Si₈O₂₂(OH)) and biotite (K(Mg,

Fe)₃(AlSi₃O₁₀)(F, OH)₂ (McGrail *et al.* 2006; Oelkers *et al.* 2008; Kim *et al.* 2023). Mafic rocks include gabbro and basalt, both of which form from the cooling of magma rising from the Earth's mantle. Gabbro is an intrusive igneous rock which forms at depth in the subsurface, while basalt forms from lava extruded onto the Earth's surface. Atmospheric CO₂ reacts naturally with these rocks on the Earth's surface as part of chemical weathering. When this reaction occurs in the context of CO₂ storage, it is termed *in situ* CO₂ mineralization (Dipple *et al.* 2021).

There are currently two pilot projects that have demonstrated the viability of safe CO₂ storage in subsurface basalt formations: the Wallula Basalt Sequestration Pilot Project in northwestern USA, and the Carbfix 1 and 2 projects in Iceland (Table 1). The Wallula project involved the injection of supercritical CO₂ into two basalt layers of the Columbia River Basalt Group in 2013. The reservoir consists of two layers of brecciated basalt, sealed by thicker layers of intact basalt (McGrail *et al.* 2017). Subsequent geophysical and

Table 1. Overview of the Wallula Basalt and Carbfix 1 and 2 projects

Project	Wallula Basalt Sequestration Pilot Project	Carbfix (1/2)
Country	USA	Iceland
CO ₂ feedstock	Coal-fired power station	Geothermal power station + DAC
Geological formation	Colombia River Basalt Group	Hengill Volcanic Group
Alteration state	Moderate with zeolites, smectites, and iron oxides recorded in vesicles and fractures.	Hydrothermally altered, with zeolites, smectites and pre-existing calcite
Age of basalt (myr)	16–15.6	c. 0.4
CO ₂ plume state	Supercritical CO ₂	CO ₂ dissolved in water
Volume injected (tCO ₂)	977	229.75/23 200
Injection depth (m)	830–890	500/750
Reservoir type	Brecciated quartz tholeiitic basalt	Fractured basalt and hyaloclastite
Reservoir temperature (°C)	36	20–50/250
Reservoir pressure (MPa)	7.7	4
Reservoir permeability (mD)	75–150	3–500
Reservoir porosity (%)	15–30 (log-derived)	c. 10 (assumed)
CaO (wt%)	8–9	7–10
MgO (wt%)	3–5	6–8
FeO/Fe ₂ O ₃ (wt%)	3–13	10–12
Carbon mineralization efficiency (%)	c. 60 (within 2 years)	60–98 (within 2 years)
Carbon price (\$/tCO ₂)	N/A	25 (CCS)/1000 (DAC + S)

Source: Data from Lambert *et al.* (1989), McGrail *et al.* (2006, 2017), Gislason *et al.* (2010), Barry *et al.* (2013), Snæbjörnsdóttir *et al.* (2018), Pogge von Strandmann *et al.* (2019), Clark *et al.* (2020), White *et al.* (2020), Carbfix (2024) and Limb (2024).

geochemical monitoring indicated that 60% of the CO₂ had been mineralized within two years of injection, with a residual plume of fluid CO₂ at the top of each basalt layer remaining trapped by the overlying seals (McGrail *et al.* 2017; White *et al.* 2020). Conversely, the Carbfix projects injected CO₂ dissolved in water into the rocks of the Hengill Volcanic Group in southwestern Iceland (Table 1). The reservoir comprises interbedded basalts and hyaloclastites (lava flows formed through sub-sea or sub-glacial eruption), with the cap rock formed by thick layers of undeformed basalt (Gislason *et al.* 2010; Snæbjörnsdóttir *et al.* 2018). Carbfix is unique as the CO₂ feedstock is sourced through both CCS (from the nearby Hellisheidi geothermal power station) and CDR (from two direct air capture, DAC, plants).

Both the Wallula and Carbfix projects demonstrate geological characteristics (Table 1) that are required for successful CO₂ storage through *in situ* mineralization:

- Both projects used tholeiitic basalts with a suitable cation supply as geological reservoirs.
- These basalts are relatively young (0.4 and 16–15.6 myr old) but have experienced some alteration. However, both contain enough reactive material to support *in situ* carbonate mineralization.
- These basalts typically have very little primary porosity or permeability and rely on post-formation processes including brecciation and fracturing to form pore space and flow pathways within the rock mass.
- The reservoirs are overlain by impermeable caprocks to trap any CO₂ that is not mineralized, such as the remnant CO₂ plume observed in the Wallula project.
- For CO₂ storage as a pure fluid, reservoir conditions must maintain a supercritical state, requiring temperatures of no less than 31°C and pressures of 7.3–7.4 MPa (Ringrose 2020).

These geological factors provide a useful framework for assessing the suitability of basalt layers in the Republic of Ireland for CO₂ storage through mineralization. Other active *in situ* mineralization pilot projects are currently underway in Oman, the UAE and Brazil, which will provide further refinement to inputs for theoretical

estimation studies such as this (Ferreira *et al.* 2024; Kolahchian *et al.* 2024).

The use of *in situ* CO₂ mineralization on the island of Ireland is a relatively recent consideration. Andrews (2023) estimated a mean CO₂ storage capacity of 65.3 MtCO₂ for the Antrim Lava Group in Northern Ireland, including both pore-space storage and *in situ* mineralization. Alexander (2024) reviewed the geochemical suitability of several igneous rocks across the island of Ireland for CO₂ mineralization, identifying the Antrim Lava Group, Connemara Metagabbro–Gneiss Formation and Dawros Peridotite as the most promising candidates. They further noted the potential of igneous rocks offshore Ireland, including the Druid Formation, but did not have access to offshore data for their study (Alexander 2024).

Geological overview

The geology of the island of Ireland reflects a complex evolution, stretching from the Caledonian Orogeny in the Devonian to the opening of the North Atlantic Ocean in the Cenozoic (Woodcock and Strachan 2012). The two basalt formations of focus in this study formed at different points in this geological history. The Limerick Igneous Suite (LIS) formed during the Mississippian (i.e. Carboniferous) during back-arc extension driven by the subduction of the Rheic Ocean prior to the Variscan Orogeny and the formation of Pangaea (Slezak *et al.* 2023a). The Druid Formation is significantly younger, forming during the Cenozoic (Dancer *et al.* 2005), and is part of the large flood basalts of the North Atlantic Igneous Province (NAIP, Á Horni *et al.* 2017). The flood basalts of the NAIP cover an estimated area of over 1 300 000 km² stretching from Greenland to Ireland (Meyer *et al.* 2007).

Methodology

An extensive database of geological and geophysical data was used to describe the two basalt layers and calculate their rock volume. Characterization of the LIS was based on a database of 2651 mineral exploration boreholes from County Limerick in SW Ireland. Some 394 of these boreholes contained extrusive igneous rocks. Significantly fewer borehole data were available for the Druid Formation with drilling in the region focused on oil and gas

Fig. 4. Location of boreholes surveyed and the subsurface extent and thickness of all basalt within the LIS in drill core. Note extensive area of LIS (Slezak *et al.* 2023a) compared with volcanic centres and outcrop from Strogon (1983, 1988) and GSI (2006, 2020). Source: Modified from Figure 1 of Slezak *et al.* (2023a), used under CC-BY-4.0.

exploration in deeper layers, resulting in most samples of the Druid Formation being left unanalysed on the seabed. Two shallow boreholes provide geological information from 28 m of core, with more limited data in the form of wireline logs and visual description of seabed samples provided by eight oil and gas exploration boreholes. Therefore, characterization relied on the interpretation of geophysical data; an aeromagnetic survey covering an area of 13 000 km² to the west of Ireland was coupled with 22 000 line-km of 2D seismic reflection data and over 4000 km² of 3D seismic reflection data to quantify the rock volume of the Druid Formation. These seismic data are presented in European polarity (Brown 2001), with a positive downwards increase in acoustic impedance corresponding to a positive (red) reflection and a decrease corresponding to a negative (blue) reflection.

Published geochemical databases were used to understand the cation populations and chemical suitability of these basalt layers for *in situ* CO₂ mineralization. Ample geochemical data are available for the LIS (Slezak *et al.* 2023a, b), while whole rock geochemistry is only available from a single sample for the Druid Formation (Chambers *et al.* 2005). Geochemical data from other Cenozoic igneous intrusions in the region were used to supplement this limited database, including dolerites from onshore western Ireland (Mohr 1982) and the Blackstones Bank complex to the north of Ireland and west of Scotland (Dickin and Durant 2002). Analogue data from the Wallula and Carbfix pilot projects (e.g. Aradóttir *et al.* 2012; Callow *et al.* 2018) and general studies of basaltic reservoirs (e.g. Millet *et al.* 2024) were used as inputs to volumetric calculations in the absence of direct data for either the LIS or Druid Formation.

The comparison of costs associated with onshore and offshore CO₂ storage was based on a review of existing literature from other storage projects in Europe, together with analysis of historic borehole drilling costs onshore and offshore Ireland to provide local context. This information was taken from borehole drilling reports and included drilling time, total borehole depth and total borehole cost. To supplement the lack of deep borehole drilling performance data from onshore Ireland, onshore drilling information from the UK was used.

A review of published literature on the public perception of onshore and offshore projects spanning CCS, CDR, natural gas

production and wind energy was carried out to understand the key concerns of the various stakeholders involved in CO₂ storage projects. Given the nascent state of CO₂ storage in Ireland and resultant lack of suitable indigenous surveys, these studies come from stakeholder groups from European and North American countries.

Limerick Igneous Suite

The LIS is a Carboniferous basaltic igneous package, comprising the Knockroe and Knockseefin igneous units. These units primarily occur as thin, laterally extensive layers of tuff, with lesser basalt flows measuring up to 400 m thick. These units cover an area of 1495 km² in southwestern Ireland (Fig. 4; Slezak *et al.* 2023a). The thickest occurrences of the LIS are found in the Limerick Syncline, becoming more discrete outside this area, with only a few hundred square kilometres of mapped exposure (Strogon 1983, 1988; GSI 2006, 2020). Analysis of 394 boreholes revealed that 95 encountered basalt (approximately 24%), while the remaining 299 only encountered layers of tuff associated with the eruption of these lavas. Basalt thicknesses in these boreholes ranged from 1 to 903 m, with a mean thickness of 89 m. It should be noted that most of these boreholes come from the fringes of the Limerick Syncline (Fig. 4). No boreholes were available from the centre of the syncline, where seismic reflection data suggest that the lava flows are thickest (Susin *et al.* 2024).

When analysed as a percentage of the total volume of the LIS rocks, the basalts constituted only 12%, highlighting the significant presence of tuff. While tuffs have been suggested as suitable reservoirs for CO₂ storage through *in situ* mineralization (e.g. Takaya *et al.* 2015), this study is focused on basalts, with volumetric calculations concentrating on the basaltic component of the LIS. It is acknowledged that this value probably underrepresents the amount of basalt in the LIS, as the thickest basalt layers are expected in the centre of the Limerick Syncline, where there is a distinct lack of borehole data (Fig. 4).

The Knockroe igneous unit is positioned stratigraphically below the Knockseefin and comprises primarily alkaline basaltic igneous material. It is characterized by porphyritic to aphanitic massive flows, dykes, intrusions, igneous breccias and flow-top breccias, as

well as volcanoclastic units such as diatremes, agglomerates, lapilli tuffs and fine ash layers (Fig. 5). Unweathered Knockroe lava flows and intrusions are mineralogically dominated by olivine, plagioclase, clinopyroxene, magnetite and apatite.

In contrast, the Knockseefin igneous unit is alkaline basaltic to basanitic in composition (Slezak *et al.* 2023a). This unit presents mainly as aphanitic flows, intrusions, igneous breccias and flow-top breccias (Fig. 5), with occasional graded volcanoclastic units, including agglomerates, lapilli tuffs and ash tuffs (Slezak *et al.* 2023a, b). Unweathered Knockseefin units are primarily composed of clinopyroxene, nepheline, magnetite, leucite and apatite, with geochemical analyses indicating significantly higher cation concentrations compared with the Knockroe rocks (Fig. 6).

Both the Knockroe and Knockseefin units exhibit zones of significant alteration, with magnetite altered to hematite and TiO₂-polymorphs; clinopyroxene to chlorite, prehnite, titanite and carbonate; and olivine to iddingsite, hematite, and carbonate (Slezak *et al.* 2023a). Extensive alteration, probably owing to the influence of seawater and the related mobilization of Ti, creates the inaccurate appearance of more evolved units such as trachytes and pantellerites (Slezak *et al.* 2023a, b). This alteration results in a significant drop in cation concentrations within the Knockroe unit while having a much more limited impact on the rocks of the Knockseefin (Fig. 6). Therefore, unaltered igneous rocks of the Knockroe unit would be considered more suitable reservoir rocks for *in situ* CO₂ mineralization and storage.

There are few data on the porosity and permeability of the LIS. Elliott *et al.* (2019) suggested that the diatreme materials may have served as mineral fluid conduits. However, Slezak *et al.* (2023b) proposed that the basaltic material was emplaced in existing faults and fractures, and thus impeded subsequent mineralizing base metal fluids, suggesting that these igneous units may be relatively impermeable. Collectively, these studies indicate that some igneous units may be more permeable than others within the LIS, but ultimately more data will need to be collected to determine the permeability and porosity of the various igneous units and their altered counterparts.

Druid Formation

The Druid Formation is a unit of Eocene volcanic rocks located offshore western Ireland, covering over 5600 km² (Merlin Energy Resources Consortium 2020; Fig. 7a). Core and seabed samples of the Druid Formation consist predominantly of basalt with small amounts of tuff, obsidian and ignimbrites (e.g. Enterprise 1996; Statoil 2004). In thin section, the basalt is described as a very fine-grained tholeiitic basalt composed primarily of plagioclase and clinopyroxene with minor amounts of opaque minerals and volcanic glass, which has been altered to smectites like saponite and chlorite (Chambers *et al.* 2005). The limited core available for the Druid Formation has been described as having 'extremely closely spaced fractures' and 'open fractures with iron-oxide staining' (Fugro 1994; Fig. 7c). This demonstrates secondary porosity being introduced into the basaltic rock mass, which could improve reservoir properties.

Seismic reflection data reveal a high degree of lateral variability. Features typical of volcanic systems in sedimentary basins are observed (e.g. Planke *et al.* 2017; Bischoff *et al.* 2021), including extensive flood basalts, volcanic edifices and possible diatremes (Fig. 8). Westward-verging lava deltas represent some of the thickest areas of the Druid Formation (up to 300 m thick) and form lobate shapes in map view (Fig. 8), with offshore seismic reflection data illustrating the complex evolution of Cenozoic igneous rocks west of Ireland. In some areas, the basaltic lava flows have been folded by the intrusion of sills into the underlying sedimentary rocks (Fig. 7d), while in other areas the lava flows remain unfolded

(Fig. 8; O'Sullivan and Childs 2021). This suggests several discrete phases of magma intrusion and eruption during the Cenozoic, with the potential for varying geochemistry and reservoir properties between these different magmas.

Seismic reflection data do highlight the shallow nature of the Druid Formation in large parts of the study area. The lava deltas are roughly 100 m beneath the seabed (Fig. 8) and overlain by mudstones and sandstones (Enterprise 1996; Statoil 2004), meaning that shallow faults through these sedimentary rocks could act as leakage pathways for CO₂. The deeper lavas to the west are located 500 m beneath the seabed and are overlain by an apparent layer of clay beneath distinct polygonal faulting (Fig. 8), which may act as a more suitable top seal. However, the large volcanic edifices may represent further leakage pathways through these clay layers (Fig. 8). The complicated volcanic geomorphology highlights the importance of detailed site characterization to assess these potential leakage risks.

Geochemical data for the Druid Formation (derived from a single sample from the 19/13-sb02 borehole, Fig. 7) shows lower concentrations of MgO and CaO relative to other Cenozoic igneous rocks from the region, including dykes and sills from onshore western Ireland (Mohr 1982) and the Blackstones Bank complex in the Malin Sea between Northern Ireland and Scotland (Dickin and Durant 2002) while having comparable FeO/Fe₂O₃ concentrations (Fig. 6). This highlights the variation expected in the Cenozoic magmas and how this could affect the availability of cations for *in situ* CO₂ mineralization. However, this single geochemical data point is unlikely to be representative of the 5600 km² area of the Druid Formation, particularly given the multiple discrete eruption events recorded on seismic reflection data, and highlights that significantly more data will need to be collected to accurately characterize these basalt layers.

Geological storage potential

Standardized calculations for the geological storage of CO₂ are relatively well established when storing it as a fluid in porous rocks (e.g. Bachu *et al.* 2007). This calculation (equation 1) considers the rock volume (V_{rock}), the available pore space within the rock volume (φ) and the theoretical saturation of that pore space that can be achieved with CO₂ (S_{CO_2}), accounting for the density of the CO₂ (ρ_{CO_2}), which varies with temperature and pressure. A storage efficiency factor (E) is often included in this equation to account for the fluid dynamics of CO₂ in the subsurface, variations in the reservoir and seal properties, as well as the injection strategy, including well design and injection rates (Bachu 2015; Ringrose 2020):

$$V_{\text{CO}_2} = V_{\text{rock}} * \varphi * S_{\text{CO}_2} * \rho_{\text{CO}_2} * E \quad (1)$$

This method, however, requires some modification when calculating CO₂ storage potential in basalt reservoirs, as it does not account for storage through mineralization. Mineralization is a critical process to consider as the minerals formed from the reaction of CO₂ with the reservoir rock will occupy a different pore volume relative to fluid-phase CO₂ (Callow *et al.* 2018). By integrating findings from CO₂ mineralization pilot projects, this calculation can be adapted to estimate theoretical geological storage potential (Fig. 2) through mineralization during the early exploratory phase. A key consideration for CO₂ storage through mineralization is the reactive surface area per unit volume of the reservoir rock accessible to the injected CO₂ (A) and the CO₂ fixation (F_{CO_2}) per unit surface area (Aradóttir *et al.* 2012; Callow *et al.* 2018). These parameters replace the CO₂ saturation and density properties in the equation developed by Bachu *et al.* (2007) in equation 2:

$$V_{\text{CO}_2} = V_{\text{rock}} * \varphi * A * F_{\text{CO}_2} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 5. Fence diagram of select boreholes through the Limerick Syncline illustrating the lateral variation in the LIS. Note the interbedded nature of the igneous rocks with the carbonate sedimentary rocks. See Figure 4 for the location of the fence diagram.

Using this equation, the geological storage potential of the LIS and Druid Formation was estimated. For the LIS, the volume was calculated by multiplying the mapped area (1495 km², Fig. 4) by the

range of thicknesses from borehole data (Table 2). As this area represents the total extent of the LIS, including tuffs, a further correction of 0.12 was applied (representing the percentage of

Fig. 6. Graphs showing cation composition in wt% for the LIS (Slezak *et al.* 2023a, b), Druid Formation (Chambers *et al.* 2005), and other Cenozoic igneous rocks which are used as proxies for the Druid Formation (Mohr 1982; Dickin and Durant 2002). (a) MgO and FeO wt% values alongside distributions from the reservoir rocks of the Wallula and Carbfix projects (Snæbjörnsdóttir *et al.* 2018; White *et al.* 2020) and the Antrim Lava Group in Northern Ireland (Andrews 2023). (b) MgO and CaO wt% values for the same datasets.

basalts as total volume of the LIS). For the Druid Formation, the volume was calculated using the thickness between the top and base of the mappable lava flows taken from seismic reflection data (e.g. Fig. 8). Porosity (φ) values from other basalt reservoirs were used in the absence of porosity measurements for both the LIS and Druid Formation; a minimum porosity cut-off of 3% was used based on the properties of sealing rocks from the Wallula project, as these have proved effective at containing the supercritical CO₂ plume (McGrail *et al.* 2011, 2017). Similarly, the maximum porosity was set at 25% based on data from global basalt reservoirs compiled by Millet *et al.* (2024), including basalts from Iceland, the Deccan Traps in India and the Panará Traps in South America. These porosity values are conservative when compared with the median log-derived porosity values of 32–42% recorded in the Antrim Lava Group in Northern Ireland (Andrews 2023). Measurements of the reactive surface area per unit volume (A) from basalt cores from the Carbfix site (Callow *et al.* 2018), range from 100 000 to 330 000 km⁻¹, while simulations carried out by Aradóttir *et al.* (2012) predict fixation per unit surface area (F_{CO_2}) for the Carbfix site ranging from 5000 to 35 000 tCO₂ km⁻². As no values for these two inputs are available for either the LIS or Druid formations, these analogue values from the Carbfix site will serve as caveated analogues in lieu of local data. However, it should be noted that given that both the Druid Formation and the LIS are older than the rocks at Carbfix, and therefore likely to have undergone more alteration, storage estimates derived from these analogues are likely to be somewhat optimistic.

Several authors suggest applying a volumetric correction (VC) to account for the ‘unproductive’ sections of basalt with poor reservoir properties. They estimate that only 10–36% of the total rock volume is usable for CO₂ storage through mineralization (e.g. Andrews 2023; Pereira and Gamboa 2023; Table 2). The corrected storage potential is calculated using equation 3:

$$V_{\text{CO}_2} = V_{\text{rock}} * \varphi * A * F_{\text{CO}_2} * VC \quad (3)$$

It should be noted however, that even with these modifications, these storage estimates will not account for a variety of other factors such as injection-induced fracturing and pore-clogging by swelling clays or the precipitation of carbonate minerals (e.g. Callow *et al.* 2018; Clark *et al.* 2020).

To account for the range of scenarios that could be present in the subsurface for rock volume, porosity, reactive surface area per unit volume and fixation per unit surface area (Table 2), a Monte Carlo simulation was run for each reservoir. This provided a more accurate estimation of geological storage potential than simply calculating the minimum and maximum scenarios. A total of 20 000 iterations were run for each reservoir to create probability distributions of geological storage potential. A total of 10 000 iterations were conducted using geological storage estimation methods (equation 2) similar to those applied in the Carbfix project (e.g. Aradóttir *et al.* 2012; Callow *et al.* 2018). A further 10 000 iterations were run using a volumetric correction (equation 3) to account for unproductive sections of basalt reservoirs. The results of these iterations are presented using three percentile values of P10, P50, and P90, where 10, 50 and 90% of geological storage iterations lie below these values, respectively.

The results for LIS are promising (Table 3; Fig. 9), with P90 values of 12 GtCO₂ (or 1.2 GtCO₂ with VC). Given that the basalt makes up only 12% of the rock volume of the LIS, according to existing borehole data, the smaller estimation is probably closer to reality. This value still represents a significant theoretical storage volume that is significantly larger than Ireland’s annual emissions; the P90 value of 1.2 GtCO₂ would provide enough storage volume for over 21 years of Ireland’s 2023 emissions of *c.* 55 MtCO₂eq (Fig. 1).

The geological storage potential for the Druid Formation was calculated for the six largest discrete bodies of basalt mapped in Figure 6 (Table 4; Fig. 9). The largest area of the Druid Formation (area A) has a P90 value of 198 GtCO₂ (50 GtCO₂ with VC). This is roughly an order of magnitude larger than the next two areas (areas B and C) (Table 4; Fig. 9). The remaining three areas of the Druid Formation (D–F) have smaller, but still substantial P90 values of 5, 4 and 1.5 GtCO₂ (1.3, 0.8 and 0.3 GtCO₂ with VC) respectively (Fig. 9). However, it should be noted that some conservative calculation cut-offs used by other authors, such as a minimum depth of 100 m used by Andrews (2023) when assessing the Antrim Lava Group in Northern Ireland, have not been applied here and will probably reduce these significant theoretical storage volumes somewhat. Nevertheless, these values compare favourably with other theoretical storage volumes calculated for sedimentary

Fig. 7. Overview of the Druid Formation basalts. **(a)** Map of the interpreted extents of the Druid Formation interpreted from aeromagnetic and seismic reflection data alongside boreholes with proven basalt. Bathymetric contours shown with dashed blue lines. **(b)** Map of the known extents of the NAIP as context for the Druid Formation basalts. **(c)** Core photo of the Druid Formation alongside interpretation from the 19/13-sb02 borehole. **(d)** Surface elevation map of the top of the Druid Formation, demonstrating the various volcanic morphologies found across the area including lava deltas, channels, and volcanoes. Source: (b) adapted from *Á Horni et al. (2017)*.

Fig. 8. Seismic and geoseismic section showing the location, thickness and shape of the Druid Formation in the subsurface. Note the lava deltas representing the area of thickest basalt reservoir. Inset: seismic and geoseismic inset showing some of the complex volcanic morphology observed on the NW margin of the Druid Formation. Note the two discrete lava flows, separated by intervening sedimentary layers, and the various volcanic vents including volcanoes and diatremes. See Figure 7 for line location.

Table 2. Inputs for geological storage estimation in the LIS and Druid Formation

Geological storage reservoir	Druid Formation						LIS
	A	B	C	D	E	F	
Area ID							N/A
Volume (km ³)	164–972	37–273	27–154	4–24	3–19	1–8	133–598
Porosity (%)	3–25						3–25
Reactive surface area per unit volume (km ⁻¹)	100 000–330 000						100 000–330 000
Fixation per unit surface area (GtCO ₂ km ⁻²)	0.000005–0.000035						0.000005–0.000035
Volume correction (%)	10–36						10–36

Source: Values for reactive surface area per unit volume from [Callow et al. \(2018\)](#). Values for fixation per unit surface area from [Aradóttir et al. \(2012\)](#). Range of volumetric correction adapted from [Andrews \(2023\)](#) and [Pereira and Gamboa \(2023\)](#).

reservoirs offshore western Ireland (e.g. [Lewis et al. 2009](#); [O'Sullivan et al. 2025](#); [Fig. 9](#)).

The theoretical storage volumes for both the LIS and Druid Formation are significant, offering gigatonne-scale storage reservoirs. The total theoretical volume of the Druid Formation dwarfs the LIS but is spread across a much larger and more operationally challenging area. Characterization of the Druid Formation is also based more heavily on remote sensing (i.e. geophysical) data with far less core and geochemical information available relative to the LIS, inevitably increasing the uncertainty in these theoretical storage volumes. While significantly more geological and geophysical data will be required to refine the storage estimation for these rocks, including the collection of more core data to measure porosity, reactive surface area per unit volume and fixation per unit surface area, they still represent a vast theoretical resource for CO₂ storage.

Cost analysis of onshore and offshore geological storage development

Several studies have explored the development of CO₂ storage projects in sedimentary reservoirs and noted the difficulty in accurately estimating their cost. This is largely due to variations in site-specific geology and engineering design, alongside the uncertainty inherent in developing subsurface infrastructure in novel geological settings ([Bachu 2015](#); [Ringrose 2020](#)). Previous studies have also demonstrated that the total volume of CO₂ stored, CO₂ injection rate and the design of injection and monitoring infrastructure had the greatest impact on cost ([Gruson et al. 2015](#)). Nevertheless, two key trends have been identified: onshore projects are typically less expensive than offshore projects; and projects which inject larger volumes of CO₂ result in a lower cost per tonne of CO₂ injected as they benefit from economies of scale ([Ragnheidardottir et al. 2011](#); [van der Spek et al. 2020](#); [Raza et al. 2022](#)). In the case of the Republic of Ireland, the significantly greater volume of basalt in the Druid Formation, relative to the LIS, provides scope for larger CO₂ storage projects which could reduce the cost per tonne of CO₂ ([Tables 3, 4](#)).

As noted above, key aspects of CO₂ storage project cost (i.e. capital and operational expenditure – CapEx and OpEx) are site specific, with borehole drilling typically contributing the greatest

cost to a project ([Ragnheidardottir et al. 2011](#); [Gruson et al. 2015](#)). Therefore, borehole costs will be one of the most influential differentiators between onshore and offshore CO₂ storage projects. Historical drilling performance can be analysed to understand the costs associated with drilling boreholes onshore and offshore. Twenty-three boreholes have been drilled in the area of the Druid Formation, four using dynamically positioned drillships with the remainder using semi-submersible drilling rigs ([Fig. 10](#)). Plotting the total depth of the borehole against the time taken to reach this depth in days provides an indication of how long a potential offshore drilling vessel would need to be on-site and can be used to estimate the associated costs. These data suggest that a vertical borehole reaching the Druid Formation (depth range 300–2500 m) would take between 7 and 30 days ([Fig. 10](#)). Costs per borehole can be estimated using average day rates from offshore drilling rigs of €325 000 and €378 000 for semi-submersibles and drillships, respectively ([Westwood 2024](#)).

Historical drilling data can also be leveraged onshore to estimate the largest contribution to CapEx. Ten boreholes have been drilled onshore in the Republic of Ireland for oil and gas exploration ([Fig. 10](#)), although most of these were drilled from 1960 to 1980. As drilling performance has improved significantly since that time, more recent data spanning from 1980 to 2019 from onshore UK were also used ([Fig. 10](#)). These datasets suggest a drilling time of up to 40 days to reach the LIS (depth range 0–1500 m). The average onshore drilling rig day rate for 2023 is €23 000 ([Westwood 2024](#)).

It should be noted that these cost estimates are for vertical boreholes and do not consider time needed for the completion of the borehole (i.e. clearing downhole drilling equipment and installing any injection or monitoring equipment) and additional costs including crew and equipment rates. Therefore, a factor of 1.2–1.4 can be applied based on historic oil and gas borehole costs to account for these additional expenses ([Fig. 10](#)). This results in a final cost range of 8–15 and 0.3–1 M€ for an offshore and onshore borehole respectively. This cost difference is likely to be observed in other aspects of CO₂ injection and storage, such as monitoring, maintenance and decommissioning, and highlights the higher costs associated with developing offshore projects relative to onshore projects.

Social licence and public perception of geological CO₂ storage

The success of any CO₂ storage project hinges on considerate engagement with diverse, yet overlapping, stakeholder groups. Given the relatively nascent state of CO₂ storage projects, learnings can be taken from other climate technology projects that straddle the onshore and offshore domains, such as wind energy. Studies comparing the public perception of offshore and onshore wind projects have largely dispelled the commonly held belief that offshore projects encounter less opposition than onshore projects owing to their distance from local communities and stakeholders

Table 3. P10, P50 and P90 percentiles of geological storage volume for the LIS

LIS geological storage potential (without volumetric correction)	
P90 (GtCO ₂)	12
P50 (GtCO ₂)	61
P10 (GtCO ₂)	214
LIS geological storage potential (with volumetric correction)	
P90 (GtCO ₂)	1.2
P50 (GtCO ₂)	7
P10 (GtCO ₂)	29

Fig. 9. Map showing the distribution of the Limerick Igneous Suite and Druid Formation, alongside the location and scale of EU-ETS CO₂-emitting entities in the Republic of Ireland (European Commission 2024) and potential CCS development hubs. Other potential geological storage sites from Lewis *et al.* (2009), Andrews (2023), and O'Sullivan *et al.* (2025) are also shown. Note only wind projects on the western coast of Ireland are shown. Source: Offshore wind project polygons are taken from 4C Offshore (2023).

Table 4. P10, P50 and P90 percentiles of geological storage volume for the Druid Formation

Area	A	B	C	D	E	F
Druid Formation geological storage potential (without volumetric correction)						
P90 (GtCO ₂)	198.0	50.0	32.0	5.0	4.0	1.5
P50 (GtCO ₂)	367.0	92.0	63.0	9.0	6.0	3.0
P10 (GtCO ₂)	810.0	243.0	141.0	22.0	18.0	7.0
Druid Formation geological storage potential (with volumetric correction)						
P90 (GtCO ₂)	50.0	11.0	7.0	1.3	0.8	0.3
P50 (GtCO ₂)	79.0	17.0	12.0	1.9	1.5	0.6
P10 (GtCO ₂)	178.0	43.0	26.0	4.0	3.5	1.3

Fig. 10. Analysis of historical oil and gas drilling time, depth and costs. (a) Offshore drilling time–water depth relationship. (b) Overview of offshore drilling vessels suitable for operation offshore western Ireland. (c) Drilling time–depth relationship offshore western Ireland. (d) Drilling cost–depth relationship offshore western Ireland. (e) Drilling time–depth relationship onshore Ireland and the UK. (f) Drilling cost–depth relationship onshore Ireland and the UK. Depth range for offshore and onshore basalt layers are highlighted with hatching in graphs (c)–(f). Source: UK onshore drilling data were provided by the North Sea Transition Authority.

(e.g. Haggett 2008; Wiersma and Devine-Wright 2014). While they note variations in the specific stakeholders involved in project development, these studies stress the importance of the participation and trust of these stakeholders throughout the development process for both the onshore and offshore domains.

The public perception of CCS and CDR is more uncertain owing to their novelty and technological immaturity. However, studies from European countries highlight the range of concerns held by local communities, which include the safety of CO₂ transport and storage, alongside the necessity of CCS and the associated risk of diverting funding from renewable energy development (Shackley *et al.* 2009; Terwel *et al.* 2012). Local communities in the US and Canada held similarly sceptical views of CDR techniques such as DAC enabling continued hydrocarbon consumption, alongside concerns about the safety of long-term CO₂ storage (Satterfield *et al.* 2023). A survey of German coastal communities revealed that there was little distinction in opinion on offshore or onshore CO₂ storage with only moderate support for either domain across the region (Schumann *et al.* 2014). The most common observation across surveys is the importance of trust between stakeholders and involvement of local communities in decision-making from the

outset of project development, both of which are crucial to achieving the social licence for CO₂ storage and echo the experiences of wind energy developers (Gough *et al.* 2018).

It is crucial for government bodies, development teams and communication experts to align to establish trust between all stakeholders. Communication strategies must consider the social context of the project as different communities may have distinct concerns, values and perceptions (e.g. Anderson *et al.* 2012; Ashworth *et al.* 2012). The Corrib gas field offshore rural western Ireland serves as an exemplary case study of large offshore energy infrastructure development with lessons for prospective CO₂ storage developers in the Republic of Ireland: the project developer (Shell) faced significant opposition from the local community from the outset of the project. Failure to meaningfully address the socio-economic and environmental concerns of the local community, alongside organizational power imbalances, political missteps and flawed policy frameworks, resulted in irreparable reputational damage for both Shell and the Irish state (Slevin 2019). The shadow of this failure in achieving social licence and the associated loss of trust in the institutions of state will probably loom large over future offshore infrastructure projects in the region.

Synergies with CO₂ sources

Geological storage has little value without a clear supply chain of captured CO₂. Several European CCS projects have adopted a hub approach, where the emissions of a geographic cluster of otherwise hard-to-abate industries are captured and sent to a single storage site, including the HyNet and East Coast projects in the UK and the Ravenna CCS project in Italy (Wang 2023). This approach helps to reduce development and transport costs, resulting in a lower price per tonne of CO₂. Ireland's point-source CO₂ emitters are spread across the country, although clusters of emitters include the cities of Dublin on the east coast and Cork and Waterford on the south coast, and the area surrounding the Shannon Estuary on the SW coast (Fig. 9). These areas make some of the most promising sites for the deployment of point-source capture technology. While there is a gap in national policy for CO₂ transportation in Ireland, the captured CO₂ from these hubs could be transported by road, rail or pipeline to injection sites onshore, or to onshore terminals which would be linked with offshore storage sites. Carbon dioxide emitters in the south of the country would have relatively short transport distances to an injection site utilizing the LIS as its geological reservoir, while offshore storage would require a more complex transport solution involving either pipelines or ships to deliver captured CO₂ to the injection site.

The co-location of CDR technologies and subsea basalt reservoirs removes the need for complex seaborne transport of CO₂; the successful albeit expensive union of DAC technology and CO₂ storage in basalt reservoirs has been demonstrated at present, albeit in a very specific environment, in the Carbfix project in Iceland (Gutknecht *et al.* 2018). Meanwhile currently unproven, conceptual designs for offshore DAC plants have been proposed, either installed aboard stationary vessels attached to injection wells (e.g. Fig. 3) or as part of floating wind turbines (e.g. Domene and Crawford 2024). A major barrier to increasing adoption of DAC is the high energy cost, which requires carbon-neutral power to have a meaningful, positive environmental impact (McQueen *et al.* 2021). This is addressed in the Carbfix project using local geothermal power. The wind resources of offshore areas can be leveraged in a similar manner, with either fixed or floating wind farms providing excess renewable energy to power DAC units and CO₂ compression and injection equipment. The western coast of Ireland has significant wind resources (de Montera *et al.* 2020) and several offshore wind projects are planned in the area (Fig. 9). Therefore, significant potential exists for the deployment of offshore DAC plants powered by wind energy resources which store their captured CO₂ in the basalt layers of the Druid Formation.

Conclusions

Both the Limerick Igneous Suite and Druid Formation offer gigatonne-scale theoretical storage capacities for CO₂ through *in situ* mineralization. Key limitations to the LIS are the lateral variability in the volcanic facies and the large amount of tuff present throughout the unit, which would disrupt the lateral continuity required to effectively store CO₂ in the formation. Current characterization of the Druid Formation relies primarily on remote sensing data with very little available core and geochemical data. Significantly more information will be required to refine the theoretical storage estimates presented herein, including geochemical, permeability and porosity data for both basalt units.

The offshore area occupied by the Druid Formation is more operationally challenging and thus CapEx is expected to be roughly an order of magnitude greater than operations onshore, based on historic costs for oil and gas exploration in the region. However, the larger theoretical volume of the Druid Formation, if proven through further data collection, does provide opportunities for projects with

a significantly larger total storage volume, which has typically resulted in a lower cost per tonne of CO₂. Given that offshore basalts in other areas of the globe, including Brazil, British Columbia and other parts of the NAIP, offer the same volumetric potential as the Druid Formation offshore Ireland, there is good economic incentive to explore this domain further as the CO₂ removal and storage industry expands.

The lack of policy cohesion between EU and Ireland creates a discontinuity between Ireland's ambition and its legislative capacity. While existing legislation permits pilot projects with a capture and storage budget up to 100 kt of CO₂ for research, development and testing, the lack of clarity around future prospects in Ireland restricts applicants to seeking significant research funding through the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency and research via Horizon Europe.

Early studies of public perception of CO₂ storage show little preference for either the onshore or offshore domain. Stakeholders surveyed in North American and European studies express concerns about the long-term safety and durability of CO₂ storage sites as well as scepticism of the relevance of CCS and CDR technologies in reducing CO₂ emissions and combating climate change. Nevertheless, the importance of trust and involvement of all stakeholders from the outset has been observed across all regions and should be foundational to all future CO₂ storage projects. Recognizable challenges in achieving a social licence to operate in other offshore energy industries in the Republic of Ireland emphasize this importance.

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